

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' HISTORICAL- PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article describes the concept of "digital competence" in pedagogy, sociology, psychology, teaching methodology. Empirical (observation, experience, comparison), qualitative (statistical calculation) and modeling (model creation, prediction) methods were used to form the methodological basis. It was found that the concept of the digital competence of the teacher is an integral element of the educational environment of HEIs and is based on the main pedagogical aspects. The practical value of the intelligence results is focused on the implementation of the rules of the digitizer model.*

Keywords: *digital competence, digital diagram, digital graph, pedagogy, digital competence, knowledge; skills and abilities; stimulation of pedagogical activity; academic responsibilities, online communication, and technospheric innovation in the laboratory.*

Digital technologies greatly expand the possibilities of providing educational information; color, sound graphics reflecting the real environment, the ability to use all modern video equipment; technology makes it possible to significantly increase students' enthusiasm for studying; • digital technologies involve students in the educational and educational process, help to fully reveal their creative abilities, activate cognitive activity, and allow them to imagine the results of their actions. ▪ From a sociological point of view, digital competence is the readiness and ability to effectively and systematically use information and communication technologies in various spheres of life based on the acquisition of information competences as a system of knowledge. is a quality, which includes: ▪ information and media competence - knowledge, skills, motivation and search, understanding, recording of text, visual, audio and video materials, archiving of digital information in the brain, as well as digital create materials using resources and critically analyze them; communicative competence - knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility necessary for online communication in various forms (e-mail, chats, blogs, forums, social networks, etc.) for various pedagogical purposes; technical competence - knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility to use relevant software effectively and safely to solve various problems, including using computer networks without harming mental health; • consumer competence - knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility that allow solving various daily tasks related to specific life situations that satisfy various needs with the help of a computer and the Internet. We answer the question of what is digital technology as follows: it is a modern form of economic management. in it, a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing serve as the main factor of production and management. Using the obtained results in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management. For example, various automatic production processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies. telemedicine services 3D technology, cloud technologies. it is possible to mention

the provision of remote medical services, the production and delivery of products with the help of smart technologies, the processes of storing and selling various goods. In this article, we will focus instead on digitization in the education system. When education is provided through digital technologies, the methods of education are becoming easier for the learners. In this case, multimedia, overhead projector, computer, laptop, televisions connected to the Internet, telephone lines, smart boards, and projectors play the role of educational system mediators.

Training teachers with such tools ensures the improvement of the quality of education. We all know that the use of digital technologies in online classes has a good effect. The opening of Wi-Fi zones and IT parks will greatly contribute to the development of the digital education system. Educators' digital there is an opportunity to develop the ability to work with technologies and organize various open courses via the Internet. This, in turn, will make educators work more with less and increase the quality of education due to competition. In addition, digital technologies will also introduce artificial intelligence technology to detect cases of tax evasion, fraud prevention, data analysis and automation of repetitive processes and increasing transparency, while big data - big data is used to store and process large amounts of data received by tax authorities, to better predict revenues and provides an opportunity to improve document exchange between payers and tax authorities.

The adoption of digital technologies is happening faster than any other innovation in human history: in just two decades, digital technologies have reached almost 50% of the population in developing countries and are transforming societies with their help in the field of health. advanced technologies based on the use of artificial intelligence to save human life, advanced technologies based on the use of artificial intelligence serve to save human life, detect diseases and increase life expectancy. In the field of education, the provision of virtual learning environments and distance learning has allowed students to participate in programs that they would not otherwise have access to. In addition, through the use of blockchain-based systems, the use of public services will be convenient, the institutions that provide them will be more accountable, and the processes will be less bureaucratic due to the use of artificial intelligence. Big data can also lead to more flexible and precise policies and programs.

Below we will touch on some digital technologies: cloud technologies are data processing technologies that provide computer resources as an online service to the Internet user. Digital technologies - Internet of Things (IoT). One of the main technologies based on digital information is the Internet of Things. It is common that many household appliances are connected to the electrical network, but gradually more and more objects of the physical world are connected to the Internet, which allows collecting information and even controlling these objects remotely. In fact, a virtual copy of a physical object appears on the Internet, containing various parameters of the object and the outside world, and allowing the control of the object over the Internet. As an example of the Internet of Things, a device such as a projector in a movie theater sends a signal to the technical support service about a detected fault and a list of parts that need to be replaced as part of unscheduled maintenance.

Digital technologies - augmented reality (AR). The most promising is augmented reality technology, which allows adding objects from the virtual world to the real world. Imagine walking down the street and seeing more information about things and people around you. Examples of augmented reality already exist and are actively used; in some amusement parks you can see the connections between objects in the physical world and the virtual world. you can already see the

signs indicating the connections. Games with elements of augmented reality are actively spreading, virtual windows and fittings in clothing stores rooms, augmented reality is already being tested in cars. At the same time, there are also issues that need to be resolved in order to actively use augmented reality technologies. For example, the accuracy of geolocation tools is still insufficient, or the computer vision technologies for connecting physical world objects with their virtual copies are imperfect. However, it is safe to say that in the near future this technology may be associated with breakthroughs.

Digital technologies - virtual reality (Virtual reality, VR). The emergence of technical devices that allow a person to be in virtual reality has made this technology in demand in the entertainment industry. Helmets and suits of virtual reality, specialized rooms allow you to enter an unknown world, all your actions are programmed to respond from the virtual world, which allows you to immerse yourself 100%. Knowledge, skills, competences, experience, values acquired by a person in the educational process serve as an integral quality of competence and at the same time potential competence. we can include the competencies that arise from the use of the competence in a real specific situation. Digital technologies cover many areas, and one of the main areas is developing the labor market by changing the requirements for the professional skills of employees of various professions. The main reason for this is 'technological advances', as a result of which machines, rather than humans, can perform more tasks. To solve this problem, a tool is needed to form a set of knowledge necessary for effective work in the digital economy. Currently, many information resources have already appeared online and offline. So, to get the necessary competencies, you can use the available online platforms, including the world's leading universities (www.coursera.org; www.edx.org; www.skillwise.com, etc.) for a fee in various areas of specialization and direction. and you can use free training courses. Online Education You can find many different educational organizations anywhere in the world offering educational programs in various formats. on the one hand, the digital economy is changing and will continue to change the labor market and the skill requirements of employees, on the other hand, the number of employees is increasing in the face of constant uncertainty about their future. Too many different media for learning will not allow you to achieve the desired result. The solution to these problems is the professional development of an employee within the framework of an individual development trajectory using a digital platform. By the transition to digital technologies, we understand the establishment of a completely new type of development of society and economy based on computers and knowledge:

Mobile social networks, cloud technologies that implement work with governments as the main components of the process of transition to digital technologies. sensor networks, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence technologies can be cited as examples Multimedia, overhead projector, computer, laptop, Internet-connected televisions, telephone lines, smart board, projectors play the role of mediators of the educational system introduced by digital technologies. Today, equipping the educational system with them ensures that students have quality lessons. Today's pandemic conditions have proven that the use of digital technologies in the education system has a good effect. We can consider the online lessons given on television as a prelude to the transition to digital education. This process proved to the student that it is possible to get education without leaving home. If we think about other advantages of transition to digital education, it is appropriate to include the following

Students will have the opportunity to study wherever and whenever they want; - students will have the opportunity to choose subjects and study from home even in remote villages where there is a shortage of specialists; - the culture of receiving and using information from the Internet is formed; - raises the education system to a new level; - dramatically reduces time and money consumption; - will have advantages in not getting lost in the "digital world" and finding a good job. Internet speed is not enough in all regions of our country today. This, in turn, prevents the transition to a digital education system. In order to eliminate this, it is necessary to carry out major works at the government level. In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of digital technologies in various fields, not only in the education system, plays a major role in the modernization of the country's education system. The organization of modern education and the improvement of educational efficiency is the practice of determining the basic skills necessary to achieve the performance goals of the competence task, as well as the development and optimization of these skills in a way that best suits the business strategy of the organization.

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